

A Study of the Interaction between Thionyl Chloride and Substances Containing the Reactive Methylene Group.

Part I. The Formation of Sulphoxides.

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During the investigations of the reaction between sulphuryl chloride and substances containing the reactive methylene ($-\text{CH}_2-$) group, it was observed that sulphuryl chloride invariably acts as a chlorinating agent (Naik and Shah, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1927, **4**, 11). It was, therefore, thought interesting to investigate the action of thionyl chloride on these substances, specially as it reacts with other compounds, giving rise to various products depending upon the conditions of the experiments.

The reactions of thionyl chloride may be roughly divided under three different heads. It reacts as—

(i) A chlorinating agent replacing groups such as (a) $-\text{OH}$, (b) $-\text{SH}$, (c) $-\text{NO}_2$, (d) $-\text{SO}_3\text{H}$, and (e) $-\text{H}$ by chlorine (Meyer, *Monatsh.*, 1901, **22**, 415; D. R. P. 201325-6, Frankland and Garner, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1914, **103**, 1101; Barbier and Looquin, *Bull. Soc. chim.*, 1912, **11**, 223; Stähler and Schirm, *Ber.*, 1911, **44**, 319; McKenzie and Clough, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1913, **103**, 687; Barger and Ewins, *ibid.*, 1908, **93**, 735; Silberrad, *ibid.*, 1921, **119**, 2029; Meyer, *Monatsh.*, 1915, **36**, 723; Pollak and Rudich, *ibid.*, 1922, **43**, 2029; Majima and Simanuki, *Proc. Imp. Acad. Tokyo*, 1926, **2**, 544).

(ii) A dehydrating agent (Denham and Woodhouse, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1913, **103**, 1861; Michaelis and Sieber, *Annalen*, 1898, **274**, 312; Meyer, *Monatsh.*, 1902, **23**, 897; Lasch, *Monatsh.*, 1918, **34**, 1653; Pawlewski, *Bull. Acad. Sci. Cracow*, 1903, **8**; Wohl, *Ber.*, 1909, **40**, 4698).

(iii) A "thionating" agent giving rise to sulphonium chlorides, sulphoxides and sulphides (Colby and McLoughlin, *Ber.*, 1867, **20**, 195; Parker, *Ber.*, 1890, **23**, 1844; Smiles and Bain, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1907, **91**, 1718; Gazdar and Smiles, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1910, **97**, 2249; Smiles and Le Rossignol, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1906, **89**, 697; 1908, **93**, 745; Michaelis and collaborators, *Ber.*, 1890, **23**, 3490; 1891, **24**,

745; 1893, 26, 2158; 1897, 30, 1009; *Annalen*, 1893, 274, 173, 187, 200; Francke, *Ber.*, 1898, 31, 2178; Rosenheim and Sarow, *Ber.*, 1905, 38, 1298; Green, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1924, 125, 1450).

It is thus evident from the literature that thionyl chloride will react in a very interesting manner, as it does with phenols and amines with which the reactive methylene ($-\text{CH}_2-$) group has many points of similarity in reaction. With these ideas in view, the reaction of thionyl chloride was studied first on malon-diphenylamide in presence of dry benzene. A vigorous evolution of hydrochloric acid gas took place, changing the colour of the solution to red, which gave yellowish-red needles. The course of the reaction may be given as follows:—

(where R = phenyl, tolyl, xylol or α -naphthyl groups or one of the R is a hydrogen.)

The above constitution of the compound follows from the following considerations:—

(i) That the two hydrogen atoms are not supplied by the phenyl group, because—

(a) Malon-dimethylamide, which possesses no such phenyl group, gives the compound $\text{SO}:\text{[CH(CO}\cdot\text{NHCH}_3)_2]_2$.

(b) Malon-monophenylamide which possesses only one phenyl group, gives the compound, malon-monophenylamide sulphoxide. If the phenyl group be reactive such a compound cannot be expected.

(c) The sulphoxides obtained are very unstable whereas those having the grouping $-\text{SO}-$ in the nucleus are very stable (Colby and McLoughlin, Parker, *loc. cit.*).

(ii) That the hydrogen atoms eliminated are not those that are attached to the nitrogen atom of the $-\text{NHR}$ group, because—

(a) Malon-dimethylphenylamide, which contains no such amido-hydrogen, reacts with thionyl chloride.

(b) Only one hydrogen is replaced in malon-dimethylamide, though it contains two such amido-hydrogens.

Thionyl chloride was made to react with the following amides:—

(1) Malon-diphenylamide, (2) malon-di-*o*-tolylamide, (3) malon-di-*m*-tolylamide, (4) malon-di-*p*-tolylamide, (5) malon-di-(1:4:5)xylidide, (6) malon-di- α -naphthylamide, (7) malon-di- β -naphthylamide,

(8) malon-mono-phenylamide, (9) malon-mono-*o*-tolylamide, (10) malon-mono-*m*-tolylamide, (11) malon-mono-*p*-tolylamide, (12) malon-mono- α -naphthylamide, (13) malon-mono- β -naphthylamide, (14) malon-di-methylphenylamide, (15) malon-*p*-tolylamate, (16) malon-*o*-tolylamate, (17) malon-dimethylamide, (18) malon-diethylamide, (19) malon-dipropylamide, (20 and 21) malon-dibutylamide (*n*- and *iso*-), (22) malonamide, and the amides of methylmalonic acid.

Of the above, (1) to (16) reacted to give sulphoxides

but in the case of amides (14), (15) and (16) the reaction products were liquids, which did not solidify even when kept in a freezing mixture. Hence they were not worked up for the present.

In the case of (17) and (18) only one hydrogen atom of the methylene group was found to be reactive, the reaction taking the following course:

This type of reaction is not unusual. Many instances may be cited in which only one hydrogen atom of the methylene group had become reactive. Sulphur monochloride reacted with malon-di-methylphenylamide giving a disulphide $[(\text{Ph}(\text{Me})\text{N}\cdot\text{CO})_2\text{CH}]_2\text{S}_2$ (Naik, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1921, 119, 379); a monochloro-derivative of the same was obtained by West (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1922, 121, 2196) by the action of free chlorine and by Naik and Shah (*loc. cit.*) by sulphuryl chloride on the same substance. Malon-dipropylamide monosulphonic acid was obtained by the action of chlorosulphonic acid on malon-dipropylamide (Naik and Shah, under publication). Such a type of reaction has generally been explained by supposing that the second hydrogen atom became sluggish after the first was replaced by the substituent. In the case of (22) no reaction takes place under the conditions generally observed in these experiments. In the case of all the remaining amides a vigorous evolution of hydrogen chloride was observed but no definite reaction product could be separated because in all probability the sulphoxides formed were decomposed during the precipitation, owing to the unstable nature of such compounds.

From the above results it can be seen that in a series like:—

(i) $\text{CH}_2(\text{CO}\cdot\text{NH}_2)_2$, (ii) $\text{CH}_2(\text{CO}\cdot\text{NHCH}_3)_2$, (iii) $\text{NH}_2\cdot\text{CO}\cdot\text{CH}_2\cdot\text{CO}\cdot\text{NHR}$, (iv) $\text{CH}_2(\text{CO}\cdot\text{NHR})_2$, (v) $\text{CO}_2\text{C}_2\text{H}_5\cdot\text{CH}_2\cdot\text{CO}\cdot\text{NHR}$ the reactivity of the hydrogen atoms of the methylene group, which

is absent in (i), starts in (ii) and goes on increasing. This can be explained as the effect of the increase of the negative character of the two carbonyl groups adjacent to the reactive methylene group in all the compounds; for malonamide, in which the two amino-groups completely neutralise the negative character of the carbonyl groups attached to the methylene group, does not react with thionyl chloride, whereas, in all the other cases, the basic character of the substituted amino-groupings attached to the carbonyl group being progressively reduced, the hydrogen atoms of the reactive methylene group are thrown into reactivity with increasing vigour. This reactivity is seen enhanced, when one or both of the amino-groups are replaced by negative groups, like phenyl, tolyl, naphthyl, etc. In the case of (v) where one of the amino-groups is completely replaced by a carboxy group, the reaction is exceptionally vigorous.

Three different hypotheses are put forth to explain the course of the reactivity depending upon the total negativity, namely, (1) polarity hypothesis (Macbeth and collaborators, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1922, **121**, 892, 904, 1109, 2169, 2527, 2601; 1923, **123**, 1121, 1925; 1925, **127**, 892, 1118; (2) keto-enol transformation (Thorpe and collaborators, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1911, **99**, 2183; 1921, **119**, 1203; 1922, **121**, 1896); (3) the combined effect of polarity and steric hindrances as would give rise to keto-enol transformations (West, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1924, **125**, 710). The course of the reaction in the case of the compounds investigated, can be represented on the keto-enol hypothesis. Taking the case of malon-diphenylamide (according to Norris and Thorpe),

The second hydrogen atom will again tautomerise and will remove the second chlorine atom, giving rise to $(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{NH}\cdot\text{CO})_2\text{C}:\text{SO}$. In the case of substances, where the second hydrogen atom remains sluggish, the second chlorine atom is removed by the other molecule.

It is interesting to observe that these sulphoxides give rise to sulphides, when heated with dry benzene in presence of a dry

catalyst such as hydrochloric acid gas and iodine. This will form a subject of a future communication.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Malon-diphenylamide sulphoxide.—Two g. of malon-diphenylamide were made to interact with 1.6 g. of thionyl chloride in presence of 25 c.c. of dry benzene, on a water-bath. After an hour and a half, when the evolution of hydrochloric acid had nearly ceased, the mixture was concentrated and the compound was precipitated by slow addition of dry petroleum (b.p. 50-60°). It came out in the form of yellowish-red needles. It was washed free from thionyl chloride by dry petroleum. It melted with decomposition at 129°. It is easily decomposed by water and alcohol giving the original amide and sulphur dioxide. (Found: S, 10.56; N, 9.52. $C_{15}H_{12}N_2O_3S$ requires S, 10.66; N, 9.32 per cent.).

Malon-di-o-tolylamide sulphoxide.—Three g. of the amide were allowed to react with 1.6 g. of thionyl chloride as above. It gave a deep red crystalline compound, melting at 129-30°. It is easily decomposed by water and alcohol. (Found: S, 9.61. $C_{17}H_{16}O_3N_2S$ requires S, 9.75 per cent.).

Malon-di-m-tolylamide sulphoxide.—It was prepared from 3 g. of the amide and 1.6 g. of thionyl chloride. It was a saffron coloured crystalline compound, which melted at 142-43°. It is decomposed by water and alcohol. (Found: S, 9.87. $C_{17}H_{16}O_3N_2S$ requires S, 9.75 per cent.).

Malon-di-p-tolylamide sulphoxide.—It was prepared like the above compound. It is a deep red crystalline compound. It decomposes above 170° and melts at 215°. It is decomposed by water and alcohol. (Found: S, 9.65. $C_{17}H_{16}O_3N_2S$ requires S, 9.75 per cent.).

Malon-di- α -naphthylamide sulphoxide.—It was similarly prepared from 3.4 g. of the amide and 1.6 g. of thionyl chloride. It came out in the form of charcoal-black needles. It decomposes at 165° and melts at 210°. It is decomposed by water and alcohol. (Found: S, 8.22. $C_{23}H_{16}O_3N_2S$ requires S, 8.00 per cent.).

Malon-di- β -naphthylamide sulphoxide.—It was prepared like the previous compound. They are deep red needle-shaped crystals. These decompose above 170° and melt at 190°. It is decomposed

by water and alcohol. (Found: S, 8.23. $C_{23}H_{16}O_3N_2S$ requires S, 8.00 per cent.).

Malon-di(1:4:5)-xylylide sulphoxide.—It was prepared from 3.1 g. of the amide and 1.6 g. of thionyl chloride. It gave deep red needles. They melt at 172.3° . It is decomposed by water and alcohol. (Found: S, 9.06. $C_{19}H_{20}O_3N_2S$ requires S, 8.96 per cent.).

Malon-monophenylamide sulphoxide.—It was prepared from 2 g. of the amide and 1.4 g. of thionyl chloride. Yellowish-red needles were obtained. The product melts at 150° . It is decomposed by water and alcohol. (Found: S, 14.54. $C_9H_8O_3N_2S$ requires S, 14.28 per cent.).

Malon-mono-p-tolylamide sulphoxide.—It was prepared from 2.1 g. of the amide and 1.4 g. of thionyl chloride. It came down in the form of chocolate coloured needles, m.p. 156.7° . It is decomposed by water and alcohol. (Found: S, 13.46. $C_{10}H_{10}O_3N_2S$ requires S, 13.44 per cent.).

Preparation of Malon-mono-m-tolylamide.—Ethyl malonate (25 g.) and *m*-toluidine (11 g.) were mixed in a round-bottomed flask, having a wide upright tube passing through the cork, fitted in the mouth of the flask. The length of the tube from the cork upwards to the bent, measured 15 cms. The flask was heated in a paraffin-bath maintained at a temperature of $120-125^\circ$. The rate at which the alcohol was allowed to distill was regulated in such a way that the ester got no chance of being distilled out. After heating for eight hours, the contents were transferred to a stoppered bottle and were mixed with twice its amount of ammonia (*d* 0.88). This was shaken for four hours. The semi-solid mass was transferred to a beaker and evaporated till it was nearly solid. This mass which was a mixture of malon-di-*m*-tolylamide, malon-mono-*m*-tolylamide and malonamide, was filtered at the pump after cooling and washed with ether to remove the unreacted amine. It was boiled with alcohol and water (1:6) and filtered hot. This kept the insoluble diamide on the filter paper. The liquid deposited white thick needles on cooling, the malonamide being kept in solution. The product melts at 165° . It is very soluble in hot water, methyl and ethyl alcohol, acetic acid, and sparingly so in cold water, hot benzene and hot carbon tetrachloride. It is insoluble in petroleum. (Found: N, 14.46. $C_{10}H_{12}O_2N_2$ requires N, 14.58 per cent.).

Malon-mono-m-tolylamide sulphoxide.—It was prepared like the previous sulphoxide. It gave yellowish-red needles, m.p. 140°. It is decomposed by water and alcohol. (Found: S, 18.45. $C_{10}H_{10}O_3N_2S$ requires S, 18.44 per cent.).

Malon-mono-o-tolylamide.—Ethyl malonate (25 g.) and *o*-toluidine (11 g.) were heated under the same conditions as stated above, and treated likewise. It gave thick white needles, m.p. 162°. It is soluble in hot water, methyl and ethyl alcohol, and acetic acid. It is sparingly soluble in cold water, hot benzene and carbon tetrachloride, and insoluble in petroleum. (Found: S, 15.0%. $C_{10}H_{12}N_2O_2$ requires N, 14.58 per cent.).

Malon-mono-o-tolylamide sulphoxide.—It was prepared from 2.1 g. of the amide and 1.4 g. of thionyl chloride. It formed deep red crystals, m.p. 168°. The product is decomposed by water and alcohol. (Found: S, 13.58. $C_{10}H_{10}O_3N_2S$ requires S, 13.44 per cent.).

Malon-mono-a-naphthylamide.—Ethyl malonate (25 g.) and *a*-naphthylamine (14.1 g.) were condensed under identical conditions. After the usual treatment, it gave reddish needles, which after recrystallisation melted at 146°. It is very soluble in hot water, methyl and ethyl alcohol and acetic acid, and sparingly so in cold water, hot benzene and carbon tetrachloride. It is insoluble in petroleum. (Found: N, 11.96. $C_{13}H_{12}O_2N_2$ requires N, 12.28 per cent.).

Malon-mono-a-naphthylamide sulphoxide.—It was prepared from 2.5 g. of the amide and 1.4 g. of thionyl chloride. It forms deeply coloured needles, melting at 170°. It is decomposed by water and alcohol. (Found: S, 11.92. $C_{13}H_{10}O_3N_2S$ requires S, 11.64 per cent.).

Malon-mono-β-naphthylamide.—Ethyl malonate (25 g.) and *β*-naphthylamine (14.1 g.) were similarly condensed and treated. The aqueous-alcoholic solution gave white leaflets, m.p. 188°. In solubility it resembles the previous amide. (Found: N, 12.32. $C_{13}H_{12}O_2N_2$ requires N, 12.28 per cent.).

Malon-mono-β-naphthylamide sulphoxide.—It was prepared like the last sulphoxide. It forms chocolate coloured needles, m.p. 160°. It is decomposed by water and alcohol. (Found: S, 11.87. $C_{13}H_{10}O_3N_2S$ requires S, 11.64 per cent.).

Bis-malon-dimethylamide sulphoxide.—Two g. of malon-dimethylamide sulphoxide were made to react with 1.8 g. of thionyl

chloride in 25 c.c. of dry benzene. After half an hour a white crystalline substance separated. When the evolution of hydrogen chloride had ceased, the reaction product was separated and filtered and washed with dry petroleum. It melts at 208°. It is sparingly soluble in benzene, but insoluble in toluene and petroleum. It is not decomposed by cold alcohol but is slowly decomposed by hot alcohol. (Found: S, 10.01. $C_{10}H_{18}O_5N_4S$ requires S, 10.45 per cent.).

Bis-malon-dimethylamide sulphoxide.—It was similarly obtained. It melts at 176°. The product is sparingly soluble in benzene and insoluble in toluene and petroleum. It is not decomposed by cold alcohol and water. (Found: S, 8.64. $C_{14}H_{26}O_5N_4S$ requires S, 8.84 per cent.).

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